

Antibacterial composite materials from wood side streams

Biocomposites are used in vast number of applications: consumer goods, toys, handles, shoes, façade and terrace elements, floors, automotive interiors, and even space applications. The use of bio-based fillers and reinforcing materials reduces the amount fossil carbon in the composite materials. According to ISO 22196 standard, the fibres from pine wood (*Pinus sylvestris*) possess antibacterial compounds, that provides added value to the fibre-reinforced biocomposites. Currently, the antibacterial property of the pine fibres is exploited in biocomposites designed for toys and materials for construction interiors.

Regional coverage and transferability

The wood processing companies are selling fibres and side streams for different applications across the Europe. Wood processing side stream exploitation and valorisation are currently local processes, predominantly occurring in Central and Northern Europe. The valorisation of low cost and low value resource to added value products is highly transferable to all wood processing countries in the Europe.

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ The use of pine wood waste and side streams in added value, innovative and profitable products
- ▶ Replacement of fossil material (plastic) with renewable material in the composite products
- ▶ Reduction of greenhouse emissions